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Project Radar Taxonomies

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Abstract:	A critical part of the Project Radar will be a careful choice of taxonomies for structuring and partitioning its data. This report covers the process of collecting, evaluating, and incorporating taxonomies into the Project Radar. This is the result of task T2.2.
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Terms and abbreviations

Blip	A visual placeholder for a specific EU funded project in scope for the SW Radar.
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CW	The Cyberwatching.eu project
CW radar	Cyberwatching radar
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Radar	Used in conjunction with CW, SWF, or TW to denote the respective radar visualisation. For example, “SWF Radar” refers to the SWForum.eu Project Radar.
SW	Software
SWF	The SWForum.eu project
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
TW	ThoughtWorks, a private software and IT consultancy firm.
TW radar	ThoughtWorks radar

Executive Summary

The SWForum.eu project is a CSA aiming to support a vast array of software related projects funded by the European Commission in the H2020 programme.

This deliverable is the first document to be published by Work Package 2, reflecting the research and eventual agreement on how to adopt and improve the Cyberwatching.eu Project Radar for the needs of the SWForum.eu project.

It is the required predecessor document to Deliverable 2.5, due later the same year, which will define the roadmap for the technical development of the SWForum.eu Project Radar. It also influences the work and results provided by other work packages; notably WP4.

This deliverable provides the necessary groundwork for a successful adoption of the SWForum.eu Project Radar by analysing the current capabilities and degrees of freedom for visualisations of underpinning data. It includes concise summaries of experience and recommendations from the Cyberwatching.eu project. It then documents SWForum.eu's decisions on which degrees of freedom it will use, and how it will do so.

The document concludes with an overview and outlook on impact and challenges the technical development team is facing.

1 Introduction

The SWForum.eu project will continue developing, maintaining and operating the Project Radar initially developed by the Cyberwatching.eu project¹.

The Cyberwatching.eu Project Radar is an adaptation of the ThoughtWorks Technology Radar² offered for adoption as open source. Cyberwatching.eu extended the scope and underpinning taxonomies to suit the software to its own needs. SWForum.eu will do the same, to customize its Project Radar to fulfil its own requirements.

A critical part of the radar customization is the careful choice of taxonomies for structuring and partitioning the stored data. This report covers the process of collecting, evaluating, and incorporating taxonomies into the Project Radar.

Section 2 will collate existing degrees of freedom in the CW Project radar ready for use in the SWF Radar. For each degree of freedom, experience gained in the active development and operation of the CW Radar will be provided, together with recommendations on limitations and choice of taxonomy.

Section 3 establishes which degrees of freedom of the radar the SWForum project will exploit, and which taxonomies these will represent.

Section 4 concludes the document with an outlook on challenges this may pose for the radar development, informing the development and production of the Radar Roadmap.

¹ <https://www.cyberwatching.eu>

² <https://www.thoughtworks.com/radar>

2 Radar Degrees of Freedom

The existing radar implementation offers many degrees of freedom for SWForum.eu to readily exploit with no or minimal changes to the source code to suit its needs. This section provides an overview of each of these, including its potential, limitations, and recommendations for choosing how to adopt each individual degree of freedom.

In a nutshell, these are:

1. Radar segments
2. Radar rings
3. Blip position (within a ring)
4. Blip size
5. Blip shape
6. Blip colour
7. Filters

The following subsections dive into greater detail for each, briefly summarising its purpose, limits, and recommendation for choosing meaningful values.

2.1 Radar segments

Radars have two primary means of visualising and locating information, not dissimilar to a polar coordinate system comprising of a) distance from a reference point, and b) an elevation angle off a reference line.

Radar segments utilise the bearing (or elevation angle) component, partitioning the entire 360-degree space into a number of segments grouping contained information into one of several classes, with each class corresponding to one of the radar segments.

Figure 1: A radar comprising six segments

To be useful, the classification, hence also the number of segments, must be two or greater. On the other hand – as visualisation almost always entails a sense of limited size – the number of classes and segments often has an upper limit beyond which meaningful and intuitive visualisation is no longer possible. The original TW Radar utilises four segments constituting four intuitive quadrants of the entire radar. The CW Radar raises this to six segments (figure 1) reflecting the Cyberwatching.eu cybersecurity and privacy taxonomy used throughout the project.

Recommendations for the SWForum radar (SWF):

- Use the radar segments to establish a top-level classification of all its elements (projects)
- Use between 3 and 6 segments and apply a suitable taxonomy.
- Choose a taxonomy that ensures an approximate equal distribution of project blips across all segments. Otherwise, one segment may be overcrowded while others are almost deserted. The CW Project radar is, for instance, affected by this imbalance.

2.2 Radar rings

Each radar segment is further partitioned into a number of rings. Across all segments, the semantics of the rings remain the same.

Radar rings can be seen as visualising some distance from the centre of the radar to the data points (the “blips”) visualised in the radar. The TW Radar uses 4 rings, whereas the CW Radar uses 5 rings (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: A segment with 5 rings

Rings are typically referred to by their index, or taxonomy term associated with it. When using indexes, rings are numbered beginning with 1 for the innermost ring, and then increase the index by one. Figure 2 hence illustrates five rings, beginning with ring 1 and ending with ring 5.

Intuitively, distance translates into continuous progression from the outermost ring into the innermost ring. However, both the TW Radar and the CW Radar use a somewhat counterintuitive approach: While distance remains the same, progression through the rings is nonlinear, indicated by the red demarcation line in Figure 2 (illustrating the situation in the CW Radar).

Both radars correlate rings with some form of software development lifecycle (SDLC) from emerging to sunsetting: Rings visualise distance from the radar centre as a form of “suitability” for adoption of the represented software. The closer to the centre the more suitable the represented software is. However, the SDLC’s point of adoption suitability lies in the midpoint of the SDLC scale, making the transition through the radar non-linear.

The CW Radar uses a notion of “project maturity” to position blips in the appropriate ring: EU funded projects have definite beginning and ending; backed by regular project reviews conducted by or on behalf of the EU Commission, the “project maturity life cycle” underpinning the blip placement in the corresponding ring closely resembles the SDLC pattern. Consequently, blips travel over time from ring 3 (young projects) via ring 2 to ring 1, indicating that the project’s outputs and results are expected to be ready for adoption. Project blips then “jump’ to ring 4 and move to ring 5 until it is removed from the radar entirely due to its age.

Recommendations for the SWForum.eu radar:

- 4 rings appear to be the minimum to usefully illustrate project age.
- 5 rings, in the experience of the Cyberwatching.eu project, appears to be ideal for visualising project maturity, including an additional phase after the end of a project.
- For visual layout, Cyberwatching.eu recommends and uses a layout that ensures that each ring has the same size to accommodate approximately the same amount of project blips. This should be the case too for SWForum.eu radar.
- However, for small and single project focussed visualisations (e.g., a widget), a layout with equidistant radiuses is recommended. The CW Radar uses this to illustrate a project’s approximate location in the radar when the user asks for more project detail to display. This practice should also be applied in the case of SWForum.eu radar.

2.3 Blip positioning within Rings

The position of a blip within a ring can carry important visual information (see Figure 3). However, neither the TW Radar, nor the CW Radar use this degree of freedom: Both Radars place blips within the ring using a random number-based algorithm to avoid positional conflict.

Figure 3: Possible blip positions in a ring

The algorithm gradually decreases the blip's size if it fails to find a suitable location after a fixed number of attempts with the blip's current size. The more recent CW Radar editions show this behaviour. This approach is safe, as neither existing radar uses blip size as a means to convey information.

However, using this degree of freedom reduces the potential of carrying large numbers of blips as ring areas are now reserved for specific information values that otherwise would be available. Choosing blip position to convey information is closely linked to choosing a suitable size for blips, irrespective of deciding blip size to convey information or not (see below).

Recommendations for the SWForum.eu radar:

- Be careful when using this degree of freedom. Blip positioning is closely linked with blip size, but also with the chosen number of segments and number of rings as both greatly influence the available area to position blips.

2.4 Blip size

Blip size can carry a certain type of information, often data on a linear scale, such as importance, budget, number of project partners, etc.

Figure 4: Different blip sizes in a radar

As with all other previous degrees of freedom (segments, rings, and position), blip size is closely influenced by the available area to express an appropriate scale of blip size: The larger a blip, the less blips can be placed in the same area in a ring (see Figure 4). This is the reason why neither the TW Radar nor the CW Radar are using blip size to convey any information – however there are other radars “in the wild” that actively use blip size for visualisation: They all have a relatively low blip count per radar, segment, and ring in common so as to ensure sufficient space available for blips of different sizes.

Recommendations for the SWForum.eu radar:

- Expecting a similar or potentially even higher number of projects to be visualised in the SWF Radar, the recommendation is to *not* use blip size to convey meaningful information.

2.5 Blip shape

Blip shape is a popular way of communicating certain type of information. Within the scope of H2020 and Horizon Europe, and in fact the SWForum.eu project, blip shapes may illustrate the type of project, e.g., RA, IA, or RIA.

The shape does not greatly impact available space for large numbers of project blips (see Figure 5). However, when used in conjunction with other degrees of freedom, blip shape tends to be drowned out

Figure 5: Different blip shapes in a radar

(conveyed information gets lost in situations of visual overload) when using many different shapes at the same time in a radar edition.

It is for this reason that the TW Radar uses only two shapes: Circles indicate ordinary entries in the radar edition, whereas triangles show that the corresponding project is a new entry (i.e., appears in the radar for the first time). In contrast, the CW Radar does not use different blip shapes at all.

Recommendations for the SWForum radar:

- Use sparingly, if at all, especially when using many other degrees of freedom.
- If its use is desired, try to limit the number of different shapes to 2 or 3.
- A better alternative might be to implement a filter on the respective information instead (see below)

2.6 Blip colour

Using colour to convey information is a very popular visualisation technique. There are many ways to use colour in a graph or radar in the case of SWForum.eu. Figure 6 shows three of many different ways to use colour in a radar. Each of the illustrated ways of using colour can be tweaked on many levels, (e.g., hue, saturation, line thickness, just to name a few).

Figure 6: Three different ways of using blip colour to convey information

Colour is a powerful information conveyor, but the way it is used greatly influences how information is absorbed, whether it visually drowns out other information or not: More colours, and/or stronger saturation tend to cause this issue.

The TW Radar does not use blip colour at all. The CW Radar currently uses full-coloured circles with a 5-colour spectrum to convey information (plus white to indicate no information available). This caused exactly the information drown-out described above, which is why the new generation will use a much more subtle approach of only colouring the circle edges.

Recommendations for the SWForum.eu radar:

- Colour is a very powerful information carrier. However, use it sparingly with a very limited palette, to avoid information drown-out.
- When choosing which information should be visualised using colour, use a taxonomy that does not cause too much information aggregation. Ideally, each chosen colour should convey one distinct value. Some data aggregation is acceptable but condensing too many distinct values into one colour loses too much information, and the visualisation becomes meaningless.

2.7 Filters

In contrast to other degrees of freedom for visualisations already discussed, filters are separately an important element of navigating and examining data visualisations as a whole.

Filters come in a variety of forms: Classic filters are some sort of UI elements that allow selecting one or more values of a given set to be shown while all others are hidden from display. Other filters representing a binary choice ('a' or 'b'; 'one' or 'all', etc.) may be implemented using other UI elements and user experience techniques.

The TW Radar uses two types of filtering; (a) displaying either the entire radar, or only a single segment of it, and (b) searching for names of specific projects that results in a list of matching project entries. The CW Radar uses the same filters plus, in addition, has implemented a third filter based on the EU JRC cybersecurity taxonomy [1]: Project entries can be tagged according to the JRC taxonomy, and users can set a display filter to show projects that are tagged with any, or all, selected taxonomy terms. In the case of SWForum, the filters are explained in Section 3.

Filters can and should be combined, much in the way spreadsheet applications and other services allow filtering data: All filter criteria must be met for a data item to be visible.

Since filters do not have an intrinsic negative impact on radar visualisation, any and all collected data for projects may be used for filtering according to requirements.

Recommendations for the SWForum.eu radar:

- Filters allow the use of complex multi value taxonomies that would otherwise be difficult or impossible to visualise using simple visual elements.
- Ensure that filters when used are clear such that it is well understood what filter is applied at the point of rendering of the filtered representation.

2.8 General recommendations

The experience gathered in the Cyberwatching.eu project leads to a number of recommendations that span some or all degrees of freedom for data visualisation outlined above. These are:

- When deciding which degrees of freedom to use in the radar, the corresponding taxonomies should be orthogonal to each other, for optimal effectiveness.
- The first four degrees of freedom (radar segments, radar rings, blip position, and blip size) are closely dependant on each other, and are greatly impacted by the expected number of projects included in any of the radar editions (or a live radar).
- Choosing the most effective combination of segments and rings for the radar depends on the expected data it is to host and visualise.
- If a taxonomy cannot be condensed without losing information, use it as a tagging taxonomy instead, and find an alternative taxonomy for rings and segments.

3 SWForum.eu taxonomies for the Project Radar

As explained in section 2, the choice of taxonomies is tightly linked with the right choice of which degrees of freedom SWForum.eu uses to visualise the wider European EU-funded project landscape.

This section will enumerate both in lockstep, i.e., for each choice of freedom chosen, the corresponding taxonomy will be explained, too.

3.1 Radar segments

Initially, SWForum.eu decided to use a radar with four segments (quadrants), adopting the four segments and the same taxonomy as the original ThoughtWorks Technology Radar.

However, sometime later in the process of assessing and deciding which further degrees of freedom to use, SWForum.eu realised that this would stop expressing an important element missing in the current CW Project Radar: Primary and secondary “objectives”. The most suitable candidate to visualise this is segment proximity – however only by having three segments in a radar is this possible without complexity in the visualisation that may lead inadvertently to confusion. Section 3.3 below describes this in more detail and how it will be visualised.

Further analysing the TW Technology Radar, SWForum.eu determined that two of the original quadrants, namely “Tools” and “Techniques”, are sufficiently close to each other: Techniques almost always require tools supporting their efficient exploitation, and tools are frequently written with that specific purpose in mind.

By combining these into one term, “Tools & Techniques”, SWForum will be able to use a three-term taxonomy for the radar segments:

SWForum’s Radar Segment taxonomy:

EC funded projects intending to deliver tangible results shall be classified using the following terms:

- Tools & Techniques
- Platforms
- Languages & Frameworks

For each project in scope, a primary and optionally a secondary classification shall be determined.

Taxonomy 1: SWForum.eu Radar Segment taxonomy

3.2 Radar rings

The original TW radar uses four rings; the CW Project Radar uses five rings. The main differences are:

- The TW Radar has no fixed chronological progression; it tracks the speed with which the entries progress, slow and fast. The CW Radar implies a fixed chronological progression based on project age.
- Projects have a longer “cooling off” period beyond their actual lifetime, which is why Cyberwatching.eu added a fifth ring to the radar.

Although SWForum.eu and Cyberwatching.eu analyse and visualise EC funded projects, the scope of Cyberwatching.eu is significantly narrower than SWForum. We therefore expect that the project will deal with a much larger set of projects.

While at first thought carrying on using five rings might benefit continuity, two reasons speak against:

1. The more rings a radar has, the less area is available per ring. With the large number of projects that we expect to process, available area per project blip comes “at a premium”.
2. In all practicality, there was little difference between projects in the “Hold” ring and projects in the “Drop” ring, as projects in these rings already ended, and there was barely any interaction with these projects happening, despite Cyberwatching.eu’s efforts.

It is for these reasons that SWForum.eu decides to return to the original four-ring model:

Assess → Trial → Adopt → Hold

with the Adopt ring still being central.

3.2.1 Project lifecycle time allocations

The original TW Radar lets blips advance from ring to ring based on the perceived maturity of the reflected product. In other words, velocity of advancement is individual per blip. The CW Radar uses a different model; presuming a *project lifecycle model* based on which blips are advancing through the radar’s rings according to a fixed temporal definition. This model is static and applies to all projects incorporated into the CW Radar editions (including the live radar). This can though pose a problem caused by the wide variance of the lifetime of the types of projects that can be funded by the different types of action. From an analysis of the current content of the CW Radar (see Table 1), the span is extremely broad: The shortest project lasts 3 months, while the longest running project lasts 73 months. Median project duration is 37 months. Indeed, only 50% of all projects run for ~3 years, when considering project extensions.

Duration	# projects	Project types (most popular)
24 months	30	CSA, IA, RIA, SME-2
30 months	18	CP, IA, RIA
36 months	130	CSA, CP, IA, RIA
48 months	25	CSA, IA, SA, RIA,
60+ months	10	ERC-AG, ERC-COG, ERG-SG, RIA

Table 1: Clusters of project durations, and most popular project types as currently displayed within the CW Radar (Spring 2021)

The CW Radar was designed to be very inclusive. The “Assess” ring includes any active project regardless of its actual duration and the Drop ring contains projects up to 3years beyond their end-date. This has led to the “Assess” and “Drop” rings being populated with projects that are either too old, or too young to deliver tangible results that could be assessed. This confuses the picture produced as they sit alongside other projects for whom the SDLC fits more normally.

Therefore, based on the prevalence of projects with a duration of 3-years in the EC funding programmes currently in scope, SWF decided to optimise the timings by which project blips are positioned in the corresponding rings for projects lasting around 3 years. SWF has though futureproofed the SW Radar though to the appearance of longer duration projects in the future

by connecting date of appearance in the radar with the project end date and only keeping projects in the radar beyond their end-date for a shorter period:

SWForum’s Radar Ring taxonomy:

Projects shall be allocated a ring based on a reference date (R) in relation to the project’s end date (T).

- Assess: $R > T - 36$ months
- Trial: $R > T - 24$ months
- Adopt: $R > T - 12$ months
- Hold: $R > T$

Projects that have been finished for more than 12 months relative to the reference date shall no longer be included in the radar.

Taxonomy 2: SWForum.eu Radar Ring taxonomy

This gives projects an “allowance” of 1 year after completion, while the radar keeps its focus on the three years before a project’s end date by filtering out projects that are “too young” to deliver mature results. By working from project end date, we hope to avoid the issues previously identified with the CW Radar and concentrate on appropriately active projects making the SWF Radar a more useful tool, simple to understand.

3.3 Blip position

SWForum.eu realised that the CW Project Radar had some issues that were somewhat detrimental to an effective visualisation of its data:

- Blip size varied, due to space constraints, but had no other meaning. This is counterintuitive.
- The CW Project Radar placed blips randomly within one sector and ring, in an attempt to maximise the use of available space. This at times could lead to some clustering that could be misconstrued to carry meaning where none exists.
- The CW Project Radar placed blips into segments according to the *most important* term that applies to the project. Realistically, however, two or even more terms may apply to a project. The CW approach completely lost that information in the radar. CW complemented the radar with a PCA to visualise the higher-level correlation of projects across several taxonomy terms. This is a barrier to understanding the information in the radar.

It is for this reason that SWF decided to find a way to visualise at least *some* correlation and conjoining of applicable segment-level classifications.

However, all existing radars are 2-dimensional for ease of ingestion and understanding, hence the SWF Radar will be, too. Since the distance to the centre location is already occupied by the radar rings, this restricts the number of segments to use for visualising segment taxonomy term correlation to three terms in the radar ring taxonomy: This way, angular proximity to either neighbouring segment can be used to visualise correlation/applicability of a primary and secondary segment taxonomy term.

This has the consequence that projects will be able to select at most a secondary applicable term, but not a third one. The taxonomy terms selected for radar segments (see section 3.1) are sufficiently distinct so that projects naturally cover at most two taxonomy terms, if at all.

SWForum’s Blip Position taxonomy:

Project blips shall be positioned within their respective Ring and Segment as follows:

- **Centre of left third of segment**
Projects with a secondary classification positioned to the *left* of its primary classification segment
- **Centre of segment axis**
Projects with only a primary classification
- **Centre of right third of segment**
Projects with a secondary classification positioned to the *right* of its primary classification segment

Positioning within these thirds of a classification segment is not relevant within this granularity of classification.

Taxonomy 3: SWForum Blip Position taxonomy

3.4 Blip shape

The TW Radar uses two basic shapes to indicate information in the radar: Circles are used to represent any ordinary radar element, while triangles are used to represent new entries. This allows for a quick distinction of “old” and “new” elements in terms of inclusion in the radar. The CW Project Radar dispensed with differentiations of “new vs old” and rendered every project included as a circle blip.

Given the Radar Ring taxonomy defined in section 3.2 above, SWF expects that new entries will *not only* appear in the “Assess” ring. New projects with a shorter lifespan than 3 years will appear first in the “Trial” ring. Indicating new entries across rings helps the user differentiate and quickly identify new entries with different lifespans.

SWForum’s Blip Shape taxonomy:

Projects blips shall be rendered as either a circle, or a triangle, in fixed editions as well as live radars:

- as a **Triangle**, if the projects never featured in any radar edition before, or
- as a **Circle** otherwise.

Taxonomy 4: SWForum Blip Shape taxonomy

3.5 Blip colour

The TW Radar does not use any blip colour, as it is using different colours to differentiate rings. The CW Radar uses colours on a 5-colour gradient to indicate a relative score (compared to other similar projects) as it differentiates rings using various shades of grey.

SWF decided to continue the greyscale differentiation of rings as a backdrop for coloured blips representing projects. Similar to the CW Radar, SWF will visualise project readiness on a Market Technology Readiness Level (MTRL)³ scale using colour.

However, there are almost countless ways how to visualise MTRL scores based on some adaptations on how to use the MTRL methodology:

- Use the original, or any variation of MTRL scales
- Equally weigh Market Readiness Level (MRL) and Technology Readiness Level (TRL), or use different weights
- Keep values separate (as originally devised), or aggregate into a single numerical value

CW modified all three aspects: Using a custom MRL scale, the CW Radar aggregated the MTRL scores into a single numerical value using weighed sums to the ratio of 7:2 for MRL:TRL – CW put a lot more emphasis on market readiness than technical readiness.

SWF on the other hand, has less mandate to emphasise market readiness: The main focus will be Open Source software – and while technical readiness and problem solution fit is on the technical level important, it is equally important to apply market readiness as a function of supporting activities and artefacts to facilitate success of any given Open Source project.

In a nutshell SWF will:

- Use a custom MRL scale;
- Weigh MRL and TRL equally; and
- Aggregate MRL and TRL into one single score.

The following sections will delve into greater detail.

3.5.1 A custom MRL scale for the SWForum.eu project

The original MTRL methodology used a MRL scale that not only covered all business activities up to and including market launch, but also building a stable and *sustainable* sales pipeline, in a very commercially informed objective to measure maturity and success.

Open Source, however, warrants a different scale: strict Commercial viability is less of importance, though the specific ecosystem developed around a particular OSS product, e.g. appropriateness of license, vibrancy of community, availability of appropriate support tools may be substituted. A viable success criterion to measure these against is its use in a production environment since this will require these previously discussed factors to be present or provide them as part of the deployment. Hence production use shall demarcate the highest MRL level 9. All lower levels will be determined in a workshop conducted as part of the first major general assembly scheduled for February 2021.

This will equalize the scale and span of both MRL and TRL, to a more fitting model for Open Source Software.

3.5.2 Weighing MRL and TRL scores

The original MTRL methodology puts equal weight to MRLs and TRLs. CW changed this to a strong emphasis on MRLs using a weight ratio of 7:2 reflecting CW's focus on market readiness and analysis of cybersecurity and privacy projects funded by the EC.

³ See WP4 deliverables for more information on MTRL

SWF’s focus is different, looking at Open Source software in particular, but across a far wider scope than CW. As indicated earlier, unless otherwise stated in mission objectives, there is no innate need to attach weight to any of the conjoined levels.

SWForum.eu will therefore treat MRLs and TRLs equally.

3.5.3 Aggregating MTRL scores into one numerical value

CW aggregated MTRL scores into comparable numeric values, using a weighted sum formula:

1. Let **M** be the MRL score on a scale from 1 – 9
2. Let **T** be the TRL score on a scale from 1 – 9
3. The aggregated MTRL score therefore is calculated as: $MTRL = 7*M + 2*T$

To avoid visual overload, SWF decided to also aggregate MTRL score tuples into a single numerical score and colour the blip in a single colour based on that score. The formula by which the single score is calculated and represented using one colour from a fixed palette has great impact on the visual message to the user.

Simulating various aggregation methods and applying a 3-colour palette, give an indication of the impact this will have on the SWF Radar (see Figure 7 below).

Figure 7: Various MTRL score aggregation methods. Numbers & percentages indicate expected coverage for 81 projects with individual scores as given in the matrices.

Figure 7 illustrates four possible ways of aggregation with thresholds for blip colours. From left to right, the aggregated sums are calculated as:

1. Simple sum (M + T)
2. Sum of weighed MRL and TRL scores as CW has implemented it (7*M + 2*T)
3. A straight-forward product of MRL and TRL scores (M * T)
4. As 3. But with adjusted colour palette thresholds

Each simulation assumes 81 projects, each with a unique MTRL score. The result are 81 aggregated numerical scores, coloured in using a simple red/yellow/green palette with thresholds based on equal distribution of base colours for MRLs and TRLs as indicated in the row and column headers. The results are individual distributions of colours: For a simple sum (1. In Figure 7), 21 of the 81 simulated projects would be coloured in red, 39 in yellow, and 21 in green. This simple simulation intends to inform which aggregation method and threshold values server SWF best. SWF expects its radar editions (as well as the live radar) to be far more densely populated than the CW Radar. It is important therefore that projects worth considering for adoption really need to stand out against those that are not. For this, simple sum and weighed sum formulae (1. and 2. in Figure 7) above are unsuitable.

A product of MRLs and TRLs appears far more suitable to the objective, However, still about 1 in 4 projects would be coloured green, meaning that projects with a TRL or MRL of 5, with suitably high companion scores, would be flagged as worth considering for adoption.

A slight adjustment of the thresholds (4. in Figure 7) reduces the number of “green” projects to almost 1 in 6 (16%). This ensures that only projects with at least TRL 6 and a suitably high MRL (8 or 9) would be considered worth adopting, and vice versa.

3.5.4 Putting it together

Based on the three aspects of a colouring scheme discussed in the previous sections, SWF decided on the following Blip Colour taxonomy:

SWForum’s Blip Colour taxonomy:

Project blips in the radar shall be coloured using a single colour from a 3-colour palette as follows:

- A custom MRL scale shall be used as defined in the Appendix
- The original TRL scale of the MTRL framework shall be used with minor adjustment in interpretation (see Appendix)
- A single numerical MTRL score shall be calculated as:
Score = MRL x TRL

Based on the numerical MTRL score, the blip will be coloured as follows:

1. **Red** for scores below 25;
2. **Yellow** for scores between 25 and 45 (inclusive); and
3. **Green** otherwise (46 and above).

Taxonomy 5: SWForum Blip Colour taxonomy

SWF will continue using CW’s approach to colour only the outline of the blip shape as that has proven useful and avoids colour “noise”. Future improvements may examine adding some transparency to red and perhaps yellow to further enhance focus on green coloured project blips.

3.6 Filters

There are many ways of adding filters to aid the user in drilling into the provided information. SWF will implement two types of filters; while the first set of filters targets intrinsic and augmented data for projects (e.g. project type, budgets, MTRL scores, etc.), SWF intends to expand on the second set of filters introduced by CW to filter projects based on sets of tags attached to projects. The first set of filters, dubbed *intrinsic filters*, are out of scope of this document.

The second set of filters, *tagging filters*, are explored in the remainder of this section. Tagging filters are a very flexible and powerful system of categorising data. Many IT systems allow flexible and free form tagging of user data and systems. Most prominent examples are Amazon Web Services (AWS) strongly suggesting customers tagging each and every resource they consume on AWS to keep control of their cloud spend; Google Mail trailblazed the way of organising one’s E-Mails not by moving them between folders but by users tagging them and implement “folders” as filtered views on the entirety of one’s E-Mails.

It has been decided that the SWF will utilise multiple taxonomies as tagging filters. However, while CW decided to use the full EC JRC cybersecurity taxonomy, this is not suitable for SWF. The application of a similar domain specific taxonomy is of advantage to allow the almost uniform tagging of featured projects using a taxonomy of direct relevance to their activities and

hence outputs. There are a number of different taxonomies available that are relevant to computing and most particularly software & software engineering.

- ACM Computing Classification System (CCS)⁴ (2012)
- Computer Science Ontology (CSO)⁵
- IEEE Taxonomy (2017) [2]
- Science Direct Keyword List⁶

Each of these cover substantially more areas within Computer Science than is relevant to the SWF and hence required by the radar. Therefore, we must consider a subset of these domain spanning taxonomies. It is clear that we can reduce down to two clear candidates, ACM or CSO. The important choice should then be at this level how we are able to reduce adequately to a usable subset without over aggregation. It is also clear that we cannot simply collapse to a single top-level feature within the chosen taxonomy since there are already desired tags including IoT, Cloud Computing, etc. as well as software engineering items that are in different domains. Following consideration, it was decided to choose ACM Computing Classification System (CCS). This will be supported within the technological implementation of the radar as the ability to allow multiple levels of filter to be applied.

The ACM CCS as a taxonomy though is broad to a level beyond that which is required by the SWF radar. At the top level of the hierarchy we will exclude a number of clearly irrelevant terms as listed below;

- Hardware
- Computer systems organisation
- Networks
- Theory of computation
- Mathematics of computing
- Human centred computing
- Social and professional topics

Leaving only the following top-level domains of CCS as having sub-elements that are in scope for the SWF radar;

- Software and its engineering
- Information Systems
- Security and privacy
- Computing methodologies
- Applied computing

SWF will start with this taxonomy alone but are prepared to respond to the success or otherwise of tagging of projects that are represented, and could therefore both add and/or take away some of the terms if their relevance is questioned.

In any case, and no matter how many filters will be implemented, all filters will be evaluated, and individual filter results combined using Boolean logic AND. In other words, for a project to be displayed in the radar, it must be part of the intersection of results of all applied filters.

⁴ <https://dl.acm.org/ccs>

⁵ <https://cso.kmi.open.ac.uk/home>

⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/index>

The SWForum.eu taxonomy (taxonomies) for filters are therefore:

SWForum’s Filter taxonomies:

1. Each of the previously defined taxonomies shall be implemented as innate filters for the user to drill into any of the published landscape radars as well as the live radar.
2. As a starting filter for possibly many additional tagging filters, SWF shall use the selected domains from the ACM Computing Classification System as outlined above.

Taxonomy 6: SWForum Filter taxonomy

4 Conclusions

SWForum.eu has chosen to implement 6 degrees of freedoms with associated taxonomies:

- 3 segments
 - 4 rings
 - 3 blip positions
 - 2 blip shapes
 - 3 blip colours
 - 1 tagging filter
- (plus all previous degrees of freedoms as intrinsic filters)

Additionally, SWForum.eu actively considers adding additional tagging filters at a later time in the project if a requirement for their implementation is found.

This constitutes the most complex combination of degrees of freedoms yet implemented in landscape radars and will have profound impact on architecture and design of the SWForum.eu Project Radar.

5 References

- [1] I. N. R. H. R. J. P. N. R. G. F. M. a. L. A. Nai Fovino, “A Proposal for a European Cybersecurity Taxonomy,,” Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2019.
- [2] IEEE, “2017 IEEE Taxonomy,” 2017. [Online]. Available: https://www.ieee.org/content/dam/ieee-org/ieee/web/org/pubs/taxonomy_v101.pdf.

APPENDIX: SWForum.eu custom TRL and MRL scale

The original MTRL framework⁷ proposed a set of TRL and MRL scales suitable for commercialisation strategies of products and services. Both scales therefore refer to production (TRL), commercialisation (TRL, MRL), and scaling (MRL).

While the TRL scale ends with technical commercial production operations of the product or software, the MRL scale is purposely designed to go beyond mere (initial) production: levels 7, 8 and 9 clearly apply only when the corresponding TRL is at level 9; in line with general business, commercial and financial frameworks where software merely in production is not enough, it has to support a scaling commercial gain to generate profit.

Clearly, this does not fit with the objectives and realities of EC funded, open-sourced software projects. Hence SWForum.eu decided to adopt the original TRL scale with slight re-interpretation of what production means in the context of the project (see Table 2). Naturally, commercial scaling of the finished product or service is out of scope for SWForum.eu which is why SWForum.eu has adopted a significantly different MRL scale for its purpose (see Table 3).

TRL	Description	Phase
0	Idea. Unproven concept, no testing has been performed.	Idea
1	Basic research. Principles postulated and observed but no experimental proof available.	
2	Technology formulation. Concept and application have been formulated.	
3	Applied research. First laboratory tests completed; proof of concept.	Prototype (Alpha version)
4	Small scale prototype. Built in a laboratory environment ("ugly" prototype).	
5	Large scale prototype. Tested in intended environment.	Validation (Beta version)
6	Prototype system. Tested in intended environment close to expected performance.	
7	Demonstration system. Operating in near-operational environment at pre-production scale.	Production
8	MVP release Minimal Viable Product state has been reached, and the product is available for adoption as a stable release.	

⁷ <https://www.cloudwatchhub.eu/exploitation/market-technology-readiness-level-mtrl-nutshell>

9	Adoption Product has been adopted by other stakeholders in production.	
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Table 2: The SWForum.eu TRL scale

MRL	Description	Phase
0	Hunch. You perceive a need within a market, and something ignites.	Ideation
1	Basic research. You can now describe the need(s) but have no evidence.	
2	Needs formulation. You articulate the need(s) using a customer/user story.	
3	Needs validation. You have an initial 'offering'. Stakeholders like your slideware.	
4	Small scale trial campaign. Eager early adopters try out your product, even if unstable or with volatile APIs.	Validation
5	Larger scale early adopter campaign. One or more beta phases see support structures and infrastructure grow.	
6	Proof of stability. Support procedures incl. issue triaging and addressing in place. Security procedures in place (e.g., vulnerability reporting). Release roadmaps emerge.	Production
7	Proof of traction. First adopters successfully integrate product into their offering(s) in production.	
8	Proof of satisfaction. Regular, reliable stream of product releases assure adopters. Retention rate of adopters steadily increasing.	
9	Proof of scalability. Community around product emerges. Responsibilities for parts of the product passed onto external stakeholders, e.g., embedded group of regular and trusted committers. Pull requests (in case of GitHub) show active involvement of the user community.	Adoption

Table 3: The original MRL scale as proposed by the MTRL framework